

ANALYZING CUSTOMER PERCEPTION AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN THE HOSPITALITY SECTOR: INSIGHTS FROM HOTELS IN AKWA IBOM STATE.

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Abstract: The main objective of this study was to examine the influence of customer perception on customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State. To achieve this objective, the main source of data was through primary source with the use of a questionnaire. The researcher adopted the survey research design approach and data were collected from 323 respondents drawn from the hotel customers' base. A total number of 312 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved in useable form representing 96.6 percent of data analyzed using the Simple Regression Model (SRM). Data generated from the study were processed using descriptive and inferential statistics and hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that customer perception had significant influence on customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State. Thus, the study recommended that the managers of hotel firms should ensure consistency across all hotel services (e.g., room quality, food, amenities, check-in/check-out procedures). Perceived service quality should not be limited to one aspect of the hotel experience. Ensuring consistency in all areas of service delivery will meet customer expectations and increase satisfaction.

Keywords: Perceived service quality, perceived value, customer satisfaction.

Introduction

Customer perception plays a critical role in shaping customer satisfaction, particularly in the hotel industry where experiences and expectations significantly influence satisfaction levels. The concept of customer perception in the hospitality sector involves how customers evaluate various aspect of a hotel, including service quality, physical facilities and interaction with staff. These perceptions directly influence satisfaction, loyalty and the likelihood of recommending the hotel to others.

The hospitality industry, particularly the hotel sector, plays a critical role in the economic development of many regions, including Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. As competition within the sector intensifies, understanding customer perception and satisfaction has become essential for hotel managers seeking to enhance service quality and increase customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction has been linked to various factors such as service quality, hotel amenities, customer expectations and the overall experience provided by the establishment (Kandampully and Suhartanto, 2020).

In recent years, customer satisfaction in Nigeria's hospitality sector has attracted considerable attention. Studies have shown that despite the growing number of hotels in Nigeria, there is a gap in understanding specific

regional variations and customer expectations in less explored regions such as Akwa Ibom State. This research seeks to fill this gap by investigating how customers perceive hotels services and how these perceptions influence their satisfaction levels. Okumos et al. (2022) opined that enhancing customer satisfaction leads to better customer retention, positive word of mouth and ultimately, increased profitability for hotel businesses.

Akwa Ibom State with its unique demographic and cultural characteristics provides an interesting context for studying customer perception and satisfaction. The state's tourism sector has seen growth, driven by both domestic and international tourist, largely due to its rich cultural heritage, scenic landscapes, and emerging hospitality infrastructure. However, despite these developments, there is limited research focusing on the specific factors that influence customer satisfaction in the region's hotel industry. Thus, this study aims to explore the influence of customer perceptions on customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State and to provide insights for hotel managers desiring to improve service delivery and meet the evolving expectations of their customers.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the influence of customer perception on customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives therefore include to:

- Examine the influence of perceived service quality on customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State.
- Ascertain how perceived value influence customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

This study attempts to provide answers to the following research questions:

- What is the influence of perceived service quality on customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State.
- To what extent does perceive value influence customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses where postulated to guide the study

Ho₁: Perceived service quality does not significantly affect customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State.

Ho₂: Perceived value does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State.

Review of Related Literature

Concept of Customer Perception

Customer perception refers to how customer interpret and evaluate their interaction with a service provider, in this case, hotels (kotler et, al., 2021). It encompasses customers' beliefs, feelings and attitudes toward a brand or service based on their experiences. When customers perceive a hotel experience positively, satisfaction levels tend to increase, leading to repeat visits and positive word of mouth.

Oliver (2020) viewed customer perception as the way in which customers form subjective impressions of a service or product. These impressions are shaped by various factors such as brand reputation, service quality and previous experiences. Zeithaml (2020) opined customer perception as the customer's impression of the overall quality or superiority a product or service with respect to its intended purpose, relative to alternatives. It reflects the balance between perceive quality and the price paid. Customer perception involves customers'

mental representation of the value of a brand, influence by its attributes, performance and emotional associations. This perception significantly affects customer behavior, including loyalty and repurchase intentions (Aaker, 2019).

The key factors that shape customer perceptions in the hotel industry are thus:

- **Service quality:** Perceptions of service quality are the primary determinant of customer satisfaction in hotels. Li & Yang (2022) in their study findings revealed that the professionalism, responsiveness and friendliness of hotel staff strongly impact customer perceptions. It was also revealed that high quality service delivery positively influences overall satisfaction, creating a favourable perception of the hotel.
- **Hotel environment and facilities:** The physical environment, including cleanliness, amenities and overall ambience plays a significant role in shaping customer perceptions (Chien & Law, 2022). Han & Ryu (2023), their research showed that high quality service delivery positively influences overall satisfaction, creating a favourable perception of the hotel.
- **Price and value perception:** Customer perception of price fairness and the value they receive in exchange of their money also significantly affect customer satisfaction. Customers often equate higher prices with higher service quality or better amenities and perceived value is a key driver of customer satisfaction (Jang et al., 2021)
- **Brand image and perception:** A hotel's reputation, often shaped by online reviews and social media influences customer perception. Tsotsou (2021) in their study revealed that positive online reviews have been shown to enhance customer expectations, which, if met or exceeded, leads to greater satisfaction.

Concept of Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction can be defined as a feeling of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing a product/service perceived performance in relation to his or her expectations (Kotler & Keller, 2016). This definition also focuses on the discrepancy between what was expected and what was actually experience. Spreng and Mackoy (1996) viewed customer satisfaction as the degree to which a customer's perceptions of product/ service quality, value and satisfaction exceed their expectations. This definition links satisfaction with perceptions of product/service quality and value, in addition to expectations.

Jamal and Naser (2002) defined this concept as a customer's overall evaluation of the experience with a product or service, influence by their expectations, perceived performance and emotional responses. This definition broadens the concept by including emotional reactions as part of the satisfaction process. Chiang and Jang (2007) in their study, they define customer satisfaction in the context of the hotel industry as the post-consumption evaluation of a hotel service experience, where satisfaction results from the fulfillment of customer expectations with regards to the quality, service and price. This definition is more industry specific and ties satisfaction to key factors such as service quality and value.

Customer satisfaction is a central concept in the hospitality industry, and it plays a crucial role in determining the success and competitiveness of hotels. The satisfaction of hotel quest is a complex, multifaceted concept influenced by various factors, including service quality, customer expectations, hotel attributes and the overall quest experience (Etuk, Awah and Akpan, 2024). Jamal and Ali (2023) in their studies emphasize that customer satisfaction in the hotel industry is a function of both tangible and intangible factors. Tangible element include physical attributes such as cleanliness, room quality and hotel amenities, while intangible factors relate to

service quality, staff behavior and emotional responses to the hotel experience. Service quality has been consistently identified as the primary driver of satisfaction, where the SERVQUAL model remains one of the most widely applied frameworks for measuring service quality in hospitality settings (Parasuraman et al., 1988). More recent studies have adapted and expanded on this model to fit the unique needs of the hotel sector (Han and Ryu, 2022).

In addition to service quality, customer expectations and perceptions of perceived value also significantly influence satisfaction levels. Accordingly, Zhang et. al. (2023) in their study revealed that a positive discrepancy customer expectation and actual experiences leads to higher satisfaction. Their study also revealed that perceived value, which balances the benefits and costs of their stay, was a critical determinant of satisfaction in hotels. Hussain et al., (2022) in their study found out that environmental and situational factors, such as COVID- 19 safety measures had a significant influence on customer satisfaction of hotels.

Relationship between Customer perception and Customer Satisfaction

Recent studies highlight the intricate relationship between customer perception and customer satisfaction in the hotel industry. When customers perceive the hotel to meet or exceed their expectations in terms of service, facilities and value, their satisfaction levels rise. A positive perception of hotel attribute often leads to higher levels of overall satisfaction (Choi and Chu, 2022).

Customer satisfaction in the hotel industry is a critical determinant of loyalty, word –of- mouth recommendations and repeat visits. In this context, customer perception plays a vital role in shaping satisfaction levels. Perception refers to the way customer interpret various hotel attributes, including service quality, facilities and staff behavior. Understanding how perception influences customer satisfaction can help hotel managers improve service delivery and customer experience.

Customer perception in the hotel context is the result of cognitive and emotional evaluations based on the various experiences customers have with the hotel before, during and after their stay. Prayag, Hosany and Odey (2013) in their study revealed that customer perception was influenced by factors such as the quality of service, physical appearance and ambience of the hotel. According to them, these factors, in turn, significantly affect overall satisfaction. Moreover, the perception of value for money plays a crucial role in determining satisfaction, especially for budget-conscious travelers (Chen and Tsai,2017).

The relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction has been extensively researched. Yuksel, Yuksel and Blim (2010), in their study revealed service quality as one of the most important components of customer perception in hotels, as it directly impacts the level of customer satisfaction. A study by Lee and Cheng (2021) suggests that hotel service quality, including responsiveness, assurance and empathy positively correlates with customer satisfaction. Their findings were consistent with the SERVQUAL model, which posited those discrepancies between customer expectations and actual service performance influence customer satisfaction.

Hotel attributes and satisfaction research highlights various hotel attributes that shape customer perception such as cleanliness, location, room quality and amenities. In a recent study by Zhao et al. (2023), it was found that hotel cleanliness and the quality of the guestroom were highly correlated with perceived value and overall customer satisfaction. These results emphasize the importance of providing high-quality tangible aspects to

improve customer perception. Ryu and Jang (2022) explored how emotional and cognitive responses of hotel services impact customer satisfaction. The authors argue that both rational (e.g. feeling welcome and valued) components of customer perception must be addressed to maximize customer satisfaction. Their findings suggested that emotionally engaging experiences tend to increase customer satisfaction more significantly than mere cognitive evaluations of service performance.

The relationship between customer perception and customer satisfaction in the hotel industry is complex, involving multiple factors such as service quality, emotional experience and attributes. Recent research underscores the significance of meeting both the cognitive and emotional needs of guests to foster high satisfaction levels. Hotels that manage to align their service offerings with customer expectations, while also delivering memorable experiences, are more likely to secure guest loyalty and satisfaction.

Theoretical Framework

In this section the theory considered relevant for this study was;

Service Performance (SERVPERF) Model Propounded by Cronin, J. and Taylor, S. (1992)

The SERVPERF model measures quality as an attitude rather than satisfaction. Thus, the model uses the idea of perceived service quality which leads to satisfaction. The model then connects satisfaction with further purchase intentions. The SERVPERF model is a modification of SERVQUAL and uses the same dimensions of SERVQUAL to assess service quality which include the following; tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy and they proposed a 22 performance items related.

Source: Etuk, Awah and Akpan, 2024.

Review of Empirical Studies

Awah, Akpan and Emmanuel (2024): Service Quality Dimension and Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study aimed to explore the influence of service quality dimension on customer patronage of microfinance banks. The method involved analyzing survey data using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found that reliability had a significant influence on customer patronage of microfinance banks. They recommended that microfinance banks should perform the promised service dependably and accurately in order to delight their customer and enhance their consistent patronage.

Akpan, Awah and Mfon (2024): The Moderating Role of Age and Education in the relationship between E-Service ease of use and Customer Loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria. The study aimed to examine the moderating effects of age and education on the relationship between e-service ease –of- use and customer loyalty among online shoppers in Nigeria. The method of data analysis involved descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that ease-of-use alone accounts for 1.7% of the variation in customer loyalty. Hence, when age was introduced as a moderating variable, the explained variance increased significantly to 30.9%, highlighting its substantial moderating effect. They recommended that online retailers should tailor their platforms to meet the specific needs of different age groups and educational backgrounds to enhance customer satisfaction and retention.

Dabiri,Ojenike and Akintan (2017); Perceived Service Quality and Customer’s Patronage of selected Banks in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. The study examined the effect of service quality dimensions on customer loyalty, the study also investigates the relationship between service quality dimensions of effectiveness and

assurance, access, price, tangibles, service portfolio, reliability and customer's patronage. The method of data analysis employed in this study was Pearson's moment correlation and multiple regression analysis. The findings of this study revealed that there was a strong positive relationship between the six service quality dimensions and customer patronage but only three independent variables namely; effectiveness and assurance, price and tangibles had positive effects on customer patronage. They recommended that banks should focus more on the six attributes of service quality dimensions.

METHODOLOGY

Design of the Study

The researcher employed a survey research design for this study. Data on both the independent variable and the dependent variable were gathered from various hotels in Akwa Ibom State. This design enabled the researcher to effectively engage with a significant number of hotel customers in the region.

3.2 Population of the Study

The study's target population included all hotels customers in Akwa Ibom State, making the Population effectively limitless.

3.3 Sampling and the Sample Size determination

Since the population size for the study was infinite, sample size for this study was determined using the Topman Formula at 5% level of tolerable error.

The formula is given as

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2}$$

Where n = required sample size

z = the value of z-score associated with the degree of confidence is 95% confidence level being 1.96 from the Z-score table.

p = 0.7 decimal (positive)

q = 0.3 decimal (negative)

e = acceptable tolerance level of error (stated in percentage points)

n = $\frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2}$

$$= \frac{1.96^2 \cdot (0.7 \times 0.3)}{0.05^2}$$

$$= \frac{3.8416 \times 0.21}{0.0025}$$

$$= \frac{0.806736}{0.0025}$$

$$= 322.6$$

$$= 323$$

Therefore, the sample size of the study was 323.

Sampling Procedure

The study utilized a convenient sampling method for administering the research instrument. This approach involved contacting respondents based on their willingness to take part in the research, as well as their accessibility and availability to the researcher.

Methods of Data Collection

The data analysis included both descriptive and inferential statistics. A simple regression analysis was conducted to assess how customer perception influences customer satisfaction. All hypotheses were tested at a significance level of $P > 0.05$.

Sources of Data

The main source of data employed in this study was the primary data source. The primary data source was a structured questionnaire which was served on respondents. The questionnaire was made up of two sections: section “A” generated data on demography, while section “B” was made up of two sub- sections which were the independent variable (customer perception) and the dependent variable (customer satisfaction).

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Data Analysis

Test of Hypothesis One

Perceived service quality does not significantly affect customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 1: Model Summary of the Influence of perceived service quality on Customer Satisfaction of Hotels

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std.Error of the Estimate
1	.711 ^a	.842	.685	.71570

a. Predictors (constant), Perceived Service Quality

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Analysis of Variance of the Influence of perceived service quality on Customer Satisfaction of Hotels

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	1519.731	1	1462.757	2581.315	.000 ^b
1 Residual	473.853	311	5.461		
Total	1993.584	312			

a. **Dependent Variable:** Customer Satisfaction

b. **Predictors:** (Constant), Perceived Service Quality

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The regression in table 1 shows that the coefficient of the constant terms (that is, the explanatory or predictor) variable. Perceived Service Quality has R-value of (.711) which indicates a positive relationship between the explanatory variable and the criteria variable. The R-square, the coefficient of determination value is (.842). This means that 84.2 percent of the variation on the Customer Satisfaction can be explained from the independent variable (Perceived Service Quality). The table also shows the adjusted R-square for the model as

(.685). But adjusted R-square is very useful in multiple regression analysis where it adjusts the R-square by the number of predictor values in the model. This adjustment allows the easy comparison of the explanatory power of the models with different numbers of independent variables. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table shows the overall regression effect in the model. The F-ratio value is 2581.315 which is significant at 0.000 and is less than 0.05 percent level of significance. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept that Perceived Service Quality contribute towards Customer Satisfaction of Hotels in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis 2

Perceived value does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 2: Model Summary of the Perceived Value on Customer Satisfaction of Hotels

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.711	.727	.847	.74762

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Value

Analysis of Variance of the Influence Perceived Value on Customer Satisfaction of Hotels

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	1483.475	1	1904.731	2742.271	.000 ^b
1 Residual	774.621	311	2.429		
Total	2258.096	312			

a. **Dependent Variable:** Customer Satisfaction

b. **Predictors:** (Constant), Perceived Value

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The regression results in table 2 revealed that the regression coefficient of R-value is (.711) which indicates that there is a strong positive relationship existing between Perceived Value and Customer Satisfaction in the selected hotels. The model summary table shows that the R-Square regression coefficient is (.727), which indicate that Perceived Value accounts for 72.7 percent of the total variation on the Customer Satisfaction of hotels. The ANOVA table shows the F-ratio for the regression model which indicates the statistical significance of the overall regression model. The F-ratio value is 2742.271 which is statistically significance at 0.000 level, since the probability value (P-V=0.000) is less than 0.05 percent, we reject the null hypothesis and upheld the alternative. This means that there is a significant influence of Perceived Value on Customer Satisfaction of hotels.

Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis of this study states that perceived service quality does not significantly affect customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State. The findings of the study revealed a significant effect of perceived service quality on customer satisfaction of hotels. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table 1 shows the overall regression effect in the model. The F-ratio was 2581.315 which was significant at 0.000 and was less than 0.05 percent level of significance. This is in consonance with the study of Han & Ryu (2023), who found out that high quality service delivery positively influences overall satisfaction, creating a favourable perception of the

hotel.

The second hypothesis of this study states that Perceived value does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State. The findings of the study revealed a significant effect of perceived value on customer satisfaction of hotels. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table 2 shows the overall regression effect in the model. The F-ratio was 2742.271 which was significant at 0.000 and was less than 0.05 percent level of significance. This is in consonance with the study of Zhao et al. (2023) who found out that hotel cleanliness and the quality of the guestroom were highly correlated with perceived value and overall customer satisfaction.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

The main thrust of this study has been presented in the preceding sections. This section is concerned with the summary of major findings. The study investigated the influence of customer perceptions on customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State. Two hypotheses were formulated to guide this study and all the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance through the use of simple regression analysis. The two null hypotheses were rejected and the alternative hypotheses accepted. This resulted from the fact that the regression results were all significant, the computed F-values for all the two hypotheses show statistical significance of the overall regression model, this means that there was statistically significant influence of Customer Perceptions strategies such as (Perceive Service Quality and Perceive value) on Customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State.

To achieve the objectives, a survey research design was used to reach out to the respondents of the hotels. The population of the study was infinite. The Topman sample size determination formula at 5% level of tolerable error was used to determine the sample size of 312. The convenience sampling technique was employed in the administration of the research instrument for the study.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were established.

- Perceived service quality has significant influence on customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State.
- Perceived value has significant influence on customer satisfaction of hotels in Akwa Ibom State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, we recommend that the managers of the hotels should enhance effective use of customer perceptions strategies to:

- Ensure consistency across all hotel services (e.g., room quality, food, amenities. check-in/check-out procedures). Perceived service quality should not be limited to one aspect of the hotel experience. Ensuring consistency in all areas of service delivery will meet customer expectations and increase satisfaction.
- Enhance the dining experience by improving on the quality and variety of foods and beverages, offering local and international cuisine. For many guests, dining is a significant part of the hotel experience. High quality food and unique dining options can enhance the overall perception of value.

REFERENCES

Agodi, J. E., Aniekan E. A., and Oladipupo, A. (2016). Determinants of customers' patronage of fast-food restaurants in Umuhia, Abia State, Nigeria; *Journal of Economic Research and Entrepreneurship Development*. ISSN 9876- 5432: vol. 2, No. 2.

- Agodi, J. E., Ahaiwe, E. O., Awah, A. E. (2017). Salesman's personality Trait and its Effects on sales performance: Study of Fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) in Abia State, Nigeria, *international Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development* Vol. 8, No. 24.
- Agodi, J.E., Kalu, A.O. and Awah, A.E. (2021). Impact of service recovery on customer loyalty of selected SMEs in Abia State, Nigeria, *journal of Business Administration and Management Science, Alex Ekwueme Federal University, 1(1), 143-150*
- Akpan, A. B. and Abdul, Z. (2009). Assessment of the impact of the of automated teller machine (ATM) on customer satisfaction the Nigerian banking industry, *Academy International journal of Nigeria, International headquarters, Ahmadu Bello university, Zaria, Nigeria,1(1),64-76.*
- Akpan, A. B. (2007). Effective of bank capitalization and confidence: An assessment of customers perception in Nigeria, *Abuja journal of business administration, University of Abuja, Nigeria,1(2),96-110.*
- Attih., O., Ikpe, I. and Mfon, A. (2017). Service marketing: A review. Akwa. Ibom. State. University (Aksu) *journal of management sciences, 2(1),19-22.*
- Attih, O. B. (2020). Packaging attributes and consumer patronage of beverages in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *British journal of marketing studies, 8(6), 1-18.*
- Awah, A.E., Mfon, A. A and Ibok, N.I. (2024). Celebrity endorsement and consumer buying behavior of Generation Y: A case study of select betting business in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. *Advance Journal of Economics, 9(1), 1-14*
- Awah, A. E., Akpan, A. O. and Emmanuel, D. O. (2024). Service quality dimension and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Advance Journal of Economics and Marketing Research,9(2), 2-22.*
- Awah, A. E., Akpan, A. O. and Emmanuel, D. O. (2024). Responsiveness and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Research Journal of Marketing and Allied Studies,12(1), 42-58.*
- Awah A. E. (2015). Insurance Marketing in Tropical Issues in Marketing Vol. I.P. 198-213.
- Awah, A.E., Akpan, A.O. and Eno, N.A. (2021). Pull promotion in the marketing of bank services: among microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, *Advance Journal of Economics and Marketing Research, 4(9), 1-15*

- Awah, A.E, Akpan, A.O. and Sampson, E.A. (2021). Public relations and savings mobilizations drive of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Advance. Journal of Economic and Marketing Research*, 6(7), 11-16
- Awah, A.E., Akpan, A.O. and Ele, L.E. (2021). Personal selling and saving mobilization drive of Uniuoyo Microfinance bank. *International Journal of Research in Finance and Marketing*, 11(10), 1-9.
- Awah, A.E., Akpan, A.O. and Mfon, A.A. (2024). An analytical study on the influence of brand associations on customer patronage of smart phones in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria: A consumer behavior perspective, *British international journal of business and marketing research*, 7(6), 21-37.
- Chen, C.F. and Tsai, D. (2017). What a perceived value and perceived service quality influence customer satisfaction: Evidence from the hotel industry, *Journal of travel and tourism marketing*, 34(6), 735-746.
- Etuk, A., Awah, E.A. and Akpan O.A. (2020). E-Marketing and savings mobilization drive of selected Microfinance banks in UyO metrolopolis, Akwa Ibom state. *An international journal of Business Marketing and Management*.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A.O. and Awah, A.E. (2022). Factors influencing the adoption of mobile apps among young people in Nigeria. A study of University of Uyo students, *European Journal of Business and Management*, 14(3), 65-73
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2022). E-marketing Strategies and savings mobilization drive of selected microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, *International Journal of Business, Marketing and Management*, 7(3), 1-6
- Etuk, S.G., Udo I.S. and Awah A. (2022), Customer relationship management and marketing technology, *Stra Mark communication consult*
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A.E. (2023). Electronic banking and marketing performance of deposit money banks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. *American Interdisciplinary Journal of Business and Economics (AIJBE)*, 10(3), 23-42. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8346738>
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Physical ambience and Customer behavior in selected microfinance banks in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, *Top American Journal of marketing*.9(1), 1-24.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A. E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Assurance and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *American journal of information technology and management*, 12(2),1-23.

- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). E-service reliability and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education, *Journal of current research in business and management sciences*, 12(2), 2-16.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Empathy and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Marketing Research and Brand Management*,12(2),36-50.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). The role of age and education in moderating the relationship between e-service security and customer loyalty: The Nigerian online shopping experience, *Michigan International Journal of Marketing. New Media and Communication*,12(2), 50-64.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A. E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Tangibility and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Business and Cooperative Research*,9(2), 1-19.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). E- Service responsiveness and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education, *European Journal of Marketing and Management Sciences*, 7(2), 13-30.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Internal marketing strategies and employee performance of commercial banks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, *American research journal of economics, finance and management*, 12 (3), 47-65.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). E-Service fulfillment and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education, *British international journal of business and marketing research*, 7(4), 41-59.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Marketing communication and consumer behaviour of betting firms in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *Advanced journal of economics and business research*, 12(3), 17-34.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). Digital transformation service marketing in Nigeria; Reshaping strategies and enhancing customer engagement, *Michigan journal of multidisciplinary research*, 12(3), 29-45.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). An empirical analysis of customer complaint management systems and their influence on customer satisfaction in the smart phone Industry: A case study of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *International journal of management communication*,12(4), 1-15.

- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). Advertising budgets and financial performance: Analysing the optimal balance for long-term profitability in Nigerian startups, *American interdisciplinary journal of business and economics*, 11(4),18-30.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2025). The role of mobile apps in enhancing service marketing effectiveness in Nigeria's financial service sector, *Holex journal of marketing and mass communication*, 13(1,17-28.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2025). Analysis of the influence of Ai-driven services on customer perception in the Nigerian e-commerce sector, *international journal of interdisciplinary research in marketing and management*, 12(1), 1-16.
- Kim, J. and Kim, W.G. (2021). Effect of hotel service quality and satisfaction on customer loyalty, *Journal of hospitality and tourism research*, 45(3), 428-450.
- Lee, Y. and Cheng, T. (2021). The impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the hotel industry, *international journal of hospitality management*,95(10,)29-48
- Prayag, G., Hosany, S. and Odeh, K. (2013). The role of the tourist experience in the relationship between destination image and satisfaction, *Journal of travel research*, 52(6), 713-725.
- Ryu, K. and Jang, S. (2022). The effects of emotional and cognitive factors on customer satisfaction in the hotel industry, *international journal of hospitality management*, 94(10), 28-54.
- Yuksel, A., Yuksel, F. and Bilim, Y. (2010). Destination attachment: Effects on customer satisfaction and cognitive, affective and conative loyalty, *Tourism management*, 31(2), 239-247.
- Udonde, U.E, Akpan, A.O. and Awah, A.E. (2022). Internal marketing and employee performance in insurance industry in Nigeria, *British, International Journal of Business and Marketing Research*, 5(1), 1-22.
- Udonde, U.E., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2022). Effect of communication and empowerment on sales-force performance in the Nigerian insurance industry. *Advance Journal of Economic and Marketing Research*, 7(11).
- Udoh, I.S., Josph, U.E. and Awah, A. (2022). Service Experience and passengers' patronage of transit companies in the south-south region of Nigeria. *British Journal*.
- Zhao, X., Zhang, R. and Xu, F. (2023). The influence of hotel attributes on customer satisfaction: Evidence from Chinese domestic tourists, *Tourism management perspectives*, 44(10), 7-12.